

Utrecht University Data Publication guidelines

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The following requirements apply to all data, data packages, datasets and/or **digital objects** published in either [Yoda](#) or Utrecht University's [DataverseNL](#). They are meant to make Utrecht University datasets more in line with the [FAIR principles](#), and to speed up the data curation process in Yoda and DataverseNL.

Metadata

Always include:

- Title
- Description
- Subject / Discipline
- 5 keywords to describe the data package
 - In both Yoda and DataverseNL, provide one keyword at a time. Click the "+" icon to add multiple keywords.
 - DataverseNL: If a PID for a keyword exists, add it under *Term URI*. You can read more about controlled vocabularies in the [guide Metadata and Documentation](#).
- Author(s) / Point of Contact / Creator(s)
- Affiliation(s)
 - Add a [ROR \(persistent identifier\)](#) for organisations) for affiliations (where applicable).
 - Both DataverseNL and Yoda have ROR lookup functionality for affiliations.
- Person identifier for all authors (creators), preferably an [ORCID](#).

Include when possible:

- If a **related publication** (e.g., journal article) exists, it must be added to the metadata with its [persistent identifier](#) (PID; for example, its DOI). The metadata of the dataset must be updated with this PID if such publication is to come later.
 - DataverseNL: add the publication under *Related publication*.
 - Yoda: add the publication under *Related resource*.
- Add PIDs to other **related resources** to the metadata as well, such as those of related datasets and related code and software. Only if a PID is not available, use the URL instead.

- DataverseNL: related datasets should be added in *Related Dataset*; related code and software should be added in *Related material*.
- Yoda: PIDs of all types of other resources should be added to *Related resource*.
- Add the data collection **dates** or date range to the metadata.
- If special permission is required to **access the data package**, explain these in the metadata fields mentioned below. A contact person/email address must be provided when restricted access is enabled.
 - DataverseNL: add access conditions in the field *Documentation and Access to Sources*.
 - Yoda: select *License: Custom license*, add a License.txt file to the main folder, and provide a contact person in the *Description*.

Documentation

- A **README file** must be added (for example: README.txt or README.md). You may use our [README](#) template. Ensure that the contents of the folders, the file formats and a list/link of accompanying software necessary to open the files are described.
- If there is no linked publication and no publication is expected to be added, add a **Material and Methods** section to the README file or in a separate plain text file.
- Tabular datasets (e.g. .csv files) must be accompanied by a **codebook** describing variables in the dataset either alongside the data or in an accompanying file.
- If personal data was processed in the project, a blank **information letter** and, where present, a template consent form must be added as documentation.

Refer to our [Documentation guide](#) for other types of data documentation.

Folder Structure and File Naming

- Ensure file **naming conventions** are sensible and consistent throughout the dataset. If acronyms are used, these must be explained in the README file.
- File and folder names must not contain **special characters** (%\$@!^&) or punctuation marks (.,:;).
- File and folder names must be **case-insensitive** for full compatibility between operating systems. Abc123 = abc123 = ABC123.
- The **folder structure** should be consistent, easy to follow and described in the README file.
- Where relevant, **file versions** should be clearly delineated. At minimum, raw data must be separated from further processed versions of the dataset.
- Use consistent **date and time formats** (e.g., ISO 8601: YYYYMMDD) to avoid ambiguities.

Data Formats

- Non-proprietary, [open formats](#) should be used whenever possible. For example, tabular data should be in .csv format (not in .xlsx or .sav).
- If it is not possible to use preferred file formats, community-supported file formats may be used. Documentation should then be added to specify which software was used and is required to read the files.
- Describe any compression methods used if files are large. Use open, non-proprietary compression formats (e.g., ZIP) where possible.

Data

- Data should be **complete**, check for inconsistencies prior to publishing. The quality and completeness of the data is the responsibility of the depositor. Pay attention to and/or explain if there are:
 - Skipped numbers in observations
 - NA values
 - Obvious outliers
 - Unexplained variable names and acronyms
 - White spaces in column names/variables. These should be turned into underscores _ or dashes - if possible
 - Inconsistent language or abbreviations
- Data should not include empty folders or **hidden files** (such as .DS_store files)

Legal considerations

- Data should be [de-identified](#) before archiving and publication. If the data package contents are not anonymous, check if archiving and/or publication of the data package is allowed. If allowed, we recommend publishing the data under restricted access. When in doubt, consult your [privacy officer](#).
- If external data was used, or the data were collected in collaboration with external collaborators, the data depositor is responsible for checking if it is allowed to (re)publish the dataset. For example, check the terms of use, consortium agreement, license, etc. if present. When in doubt, consult the [data steward](#).
- A [license](#) must be added to the data package. The Creative Commons Attribution (CC-BY) or CC0 licences are recommended.
- If the data package is to be published under Restricted Access, a [Custom license](#) must be added. There should be a valid reason to publish under Restricted Access (e.g., personal data, confidential data or intellectual property).

Code

- When present, add (commented) **preprocessing and analysis code** to the data package. If appropriate, the code can also be deposited elsewhere (e.g., [on GitHub](#)) and referred to with its PID or URL.
- If no code was used, a description of the steps taken to analyse/study the data must be added to the data package instead.

Glossary

Codebook: We use the term codebook loosely to refer to a file that describes data level metadata, particularly variable descriptions. [Here is an example](#).

Custom license: A legal permit defined by a data depositor for potential data users. Custom licenses, as opposed to pre-defined data licenses, are used when specific data re-use requirements must be met. They are commonly used when personal, confidential, critical or other forms of sensitive data are at hand. When dealing with personal data you might often use a [Data Transfer agreement or a Data Use agreement](#) as a custom license.

Data license: A legal permit used by a data depositor for potential data users. Determines the conditions and limitations under which the data may be re-used. The [creative common licenses](#) are good examples.

Digital object: Any form of digital content in any format.

Metadata (data-level): Metadata is data about data. We use this term to differentiate the generic metadata that describes the whole dataset, from the metadata used to describe the variable names, conditions and other parameters necessary to adequately interpret the raw/processed data.

Metadata (generic): Metadata is data about data. The term generic metadata is used to specify the information which pertains to the entire dataset or digital object such as title, language, authors, subject, etc. It is the metadata that is necessary to make the data findable.

Persistent identifier (PID): A long-lasting reference to a digital object. It is less likely to break than a common URL. Examples of PIDs are Digital Object Identifiers (DOI), ORCID (a PID for people) and Research Organization Registry ID (ROR; for organizations) and URI (a PID for vocabulary terms).